

An Integrated Geographic Information System for Intelligent Transport System for the Road Network of Cyprus

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Abstract

Following the EU ITS Directive 2010/40/EU, as well as the Delegated Regulations 885/2013, 886/2013, 962/2015, and 2017/1926, the Public Works Department of Cyprus in collaboration with the KIOS Research and Innovation Centre of Excellence of the University of Cyprus, have developed a complete Geographical Information System referred to as GNOSIS platform, to support the introduction of Intelligent Transport Systems in the island. This paper describes the development cycle of this system, from the requirement collection and system architecture to the delivered platform. In addition, this paper demonstrates how information systems related to critical infrastructures, such as road networks, can be developed using only open-source tools, without compromising the quality of the provided services. Finally, it is noted that the development of the GNOSIS platform is a step towards the achievement of the goals of the EU ITS Directive 2010/40/EU and in full harmony with The European Green Deal in Cyprus.

Keywords: Data Management, GIS, ITS, Road Network, Public Sector, Mobile Application, QGIS, Cyprus

Introduction

Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) and Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) have seen significant growth in the last few decades. As technology becomes less expensive, smarter, and pervasive coupled with investment in digital infrastructure, the transportation sector evolved to embrace improved traffic management and control functions. Similarly, in-vehicle technology has evolved to support advanced features and services leveraging the plethora of sensors in and around the vehicle. Detecting traffic and road conditions, helping drivers reduce their response time, incident prevention and adapting the vehicles' behaviour to improve road safety are some of the examples. As an enabler, the ITS Directive 2010/40/EU revolves around the optimal use of road traffic and travel data, continuity of traffic and freight management, road safety and security and linking vehicle and transport infrastructure [1]. It is noteworthy that the world's first regulatory standard for Intelligent Speed Assistance (ISA) technology has been published in the official journal of the European Union (EU), preparing car manufacturers and

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members states for the introduction of ISA in Europe which is expected to reduce road collisions by 30% and deaths caused by accidents by 20% [2,3].

In 2017, the EU report “High-Level Group on the Competitiveness and Sustainable Growth of the Automotive Industry in the European Union, Gear 2030” recognises the importance of automated driving and encouraged the member states to invest in the connectivity of vehicles and the development of supporting infrastructure [4]. In addition, at the end of 2019 the EU announced “The European Green Deal”, where it recognises that within the EU, the transport sector is responsible for around 25% of the greenhouse gas emissions, making it the second-biggest emitting sector after energy. The EU has adopted legislation across multiple policy areas to implement its international commitments on climate change. The 2020 greenhouse gas emission reduction targets, set by EU leaders in 2007 and achieved by 2017, the EU had reduced its emissions by almost 22% compared to 1990, reaching the target three years ahead of schedule. In December 2020, the binding EU target for reduction in greenhouse gas emissions was raised from 40% to 55%, to be achieved by 2030 [5].

Considering, “The European Green Deal” and several relevant directives and regulations, all EU members states are working to ensure the transition to the new era of mobility with a special attention in reducing the energy dependence of the transport modes on fossil fuels, as well as the increase of digitalisation of the transport sector and the operation of sustainable multimodal mobility services [6].

The Ministry of Transport, Communications and Works (MTCW) in Cyprus, in its efforts to introduce Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) in the island, in cooperation with the KIOS Research and Innovation Centre of Excellence (KIOS CoE) of the University of Cyprus, are undertaking numerous research activities on ITS. These activities are related to the EU Directives and Regulations. Under this initiative, an integrated GIS platform with the acronym “GNOSIS” (Geographic INformatiOn System for Intelligent Transport System) has been developed to collect, store, analyse, manage, and disseminate data regarding mobility. This platform consists of three main components: a Desktop application, a Mobile application and a Web Portal which is going to become the new National Access Point (NAP) of Cyprus.

Objectives

The main objectives of this paper are: 1) to demonstrate how Cyprus is working in complying with its obligations derived from the ITS directive and other relevant obligations and 2) to showcase its newly developed GIS system for ITS, which was built using only open-source components. These objectives were met under the collaboration of the MTCW with the academia by developing the necessary digital infrastructure to manage the road network of Cyprus efficiently and prepare for the introduction of ITS services to the island [7], while reducing the cost of licensing fees using open-source software. This new digital infrastructure is focused on the activities of the Public Works Department (PWD) of Cyprus, as the road authority for the main road network of Cyprus which consist of the TEN-T road network in

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Cyprus (approximate 330 Km) and Main Roads network (approximate 2,400 Km) (Figure 1). Furthermore, the MTCW and PWD, by working with the KIOS CoE were able to use the latest research developments around ITS directly from the academia.

Figure 1 - Road network maintained by PWD

Method

The development of the “GNOSIS” platform is based on a hybrid agile-waterfall methodology, integrating the elements from both Agile and Waterfall software development life cycle (SDLC) development [8–10]. The Waterfall development methodology was used for the user needs and specifications analysis. This stage was split into smaller phases and in each phase, a report was prepared by the analysts which was assessed and approved by the MTCW. This process prevented any miscommunication between the analysts, developers, and stakeholders for the usage of the platform [8].

Once the specifications and the main functions of the system were agreed upon, they were split into sub-functions, and the development phase started following the Agile development methodology. At this stage, every function of the platform was developed tested and presented to the MTCW for feedback before the final submission [8]. This was an iterative process in which each iteration was a complete software package which was then integrated with the main system. That includes requirements analysis, architecture planning and design, coding and development as well testing and documentation (Figure 2). Cycles kept short with the developing team focusing on adapting to the current business environment [9,11].

Figure 2 - Hybrid agile-waterfall methodology approach

Standardization

To ensure the sustainability and compatibility of the new platform with existing and upcoming EU regulations, the GNOSIS platform database was built under the INSPIRE Data Specification for the spatial data theme Transport Networks. The “Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community” or INSPIRE, is a data framework derived from the INSPIRE directive [12]. This directive aims to establish an EU wide infrastructure for spatial information in Europe intending to make spatial or geographical information more accessible and interoperable for a wide range of purposes supporting sustainable development. The INSPIRE directive is clearly stated in the ITS directive that it should be compatible with the ITS development in the EU [1].

System architecture

While the GNOSIS platform is already in use, it is still being developed to incorporate further functionalities. The system architecture of the GNOSIS platform consists of 5 functional elements [8] (Figure 3) as follows:

- 1) External Database Services which through an Extract Transform Load (ETL) function, access databases from other organisations which provide data related to transport such as environmental data.
- 2) GNOSIS Database Server, which consists of a dataset collection of spatial data and related attribute tables of the transport network of Cyprus.
- 3) Application Server, which communicates the data to the end-user via the front-end of the “GNOSIS” platform, through three interfaces.
- 4) Identity and Access Management (IAM), which can give users the ability to sign in with a single set of credentials to gain access to multiple services and resources depending on their access level.
- 5) Admin Console, which is the environment where the developers can upload their code for new or enhanced functions of GNOSIS.
- 6) User Interfaces consist of Desktop software, Mobile and Web applications. These interfaces are

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described further in the following sections.

Figure 3 – GNOSIS System Architecture

Results and Evaluation

By developing the GNOSIS platform, several datasets which were spread across the departments with various forms were stored in a structured form in the database creating added value to the PWD. Currently, the GNOSIS Database consists of around 10GB of data with more than 50 unique datasets which are structured to enhance the interoperability of data within the organisation. Before GNOSIS, if one department needed for example inputs from another department, this process could take up to a week while now all data are instantly available to all employees saving a lot of time from their day-to-day work. In addition, the desktop version integrates efficiently with the mobile application for assigning tasks and monitoring their progress for PWD field working teams while at the same time the GNOSIS web portal supports the MTCW obligations to disseminate mobility-related data to the public. These three interfaces are described below.

Desktop Application

The GNOSIS desktop user interface was developed as a toolkit within the open-source software QGIS. This toolkit consists of 100 QGIS-based Graphical User Interface (GUI) plugins that link the QGIS environment with the application server and the GNOSIS Database (Figure 4). This approach allows having a modular software where each user depending on their access level, can access different plugins. More specific, these plugins were divided into 8 categories which are linked to specific departments of the Public Works department. These categories include:

- 1) Road network-related plugins such as network corrections and creation of new network elements in cases a new network is constructed.
- 2) Maintenance-related plugins, such as plugins for scheduling maintenance activities in the road network.

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- 3) Road Furniture plugins for managing road furniture such as traffic signs and safety barriers.
- 4) Public Transport plugins related to public transport routes and bus stops.
- 5) Bridges plugins related to bridges managed by the PWD, for example, to add maintenance dates, inspection comments or construction documents.
- 6) Accidents' plugins that related to spatial allocation of accidents and hot spot analysis.
- 7) Mobile data collection plugins that are related to fieldwork and data collected from the mobile application.
- 8) Supplementary plugins that contain support functions for the users such as layers management, map preparation using PWD templates, export data etc.

Figure 4 – GNOSIS plugins categories

The use of the 'GNOSIS' toolkit assists PWD employees to increase their productivity and accountability on a departmental level. In addition, it was noted by the management of PWD, that errors in data collection, analysis and storage were minimised and thus the quality of produced data was significantly improved.

Mobile Application

Focusing on data collection, through the requirements analysis it was identified that the pre-existent processes of data collection were time-consuming, which were mainly based on handwritten notes and pictures from the site. The GNOSIS mobile app (Figure 5) is an Android-based application which was developed to provide a simple tool to the PWD field workers, not only to collect data from the field but also to help them with the management of any ongoing field works. Through the GNOSIS desktop, executive engineers can plan and allocate field works and the mobile app users can be notified about their assigned tasks. In addition, the mobile app provides the necessary functionalities to collect data from the field such as road furniture, to populate the GNOSIS database. Finally, the app has a specific, simple to use interface that allows users to collect data for issues in the road network which are identified by field workers such as potholes, damaged traffic signs or damages on the road infrastructure.

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Figure 5 – GNOSIS mobile app

Web Application

The web portal of GNOSIS aims to substitute the existing website of the MTCW for traffic information. The existing website with the name “DIAVLOS” is currently hosted on the link <http://www.traffic4cyprus.org.cy/> and it provides basic traffic information, a route planning tool, information about public transport, parking, and bike network. However, following the ITS directive as well as the Delegated Regulations 885/2013, 886/2013, 962/2015, and 2017/1926, all the EU Member States are required to develop their National Access Points; to enable easy access, exchange, and reuse of transport-related data, to support an EU-wide interoperable travel and traffic services to end-users [13–16]. Therefore, the MTCW and the PWD in their efforts to comply with the Delegated Regulations decided to use the GNOSIS web portal as the new NAP for Cyprus (Figure 6). The GNOSIS web portal is not yet published to the public, but it is in its final stage. This portal consists of two main sections which are, a digital map with real-time traffic information and an Open Data portal where users can download any data related to transport owned by the MTCW. The web portal is expected to be live in Q2 2022 at the same website of “DIAVLOS”.

Figure 6 – GNOSIS Web portal / Cyprus National Access Point

Conclusions

This paper aimed to demonstrate how Cyprus managed to implement an integrated GI system using only open-source components, which is used as the foundation of ITS on the island. The developed system consists of a good example of how open-source software can be combined, to provide a complete solution for collecting, storing, managing, analysing, and disseminating geographical information data. The modular approach of the toolkit allows the PWD to manage the access levels of the GNOSIS Desktop allowing better control of the data access improving at the same time the quality of the data stored in the database. In addition, the developed mobile app is helping PWD to manage field works better, improve the communication of different field teams, as well as to collect valuable data from the road network. Finally, the web portal provides a single access point for any mobility data establishing links between the road authority and those intending to be involved in research in ITS or creating and providing mobility solutions and services using open data fulfilling at the same time Cyprus obligations related to the ITS directive 2010/40/EU and relevant EU Delegated Regulations.

Future Work

Given the commitment of the EU for Greener and more sustainable transport, as well as the commitment of the MTCW to reducing CO₂ emissions and reducing the traffic, the PWD is continuing its collaboration with KIOS CoE under a project funded by the Recovery and Resilience Facility fund to build on top of GNOSIS a Digital Twin of the road infrastructure of Cyprus. This Digital Twin will further enhance GNOSIS functionalities to create a real-time representation of the road network of the island which will be used to test different scenarios, reduce road congestion, and increase sustainable urban mobility. At the same time, this Digital Twin will be used for monitoring the efficiency of the road infrastructure and assist in decision making to take mitigation measurements where needed. This project started in January 2022 and is expected to finish by April 2025.

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